

TEACHERS' PERCEPTIONS ON THE ROLE PLAYED BY A PRINCIPAL'S LEADERSHIP REGARDING SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A CASE STUDY OF A HIGH SCHOOL IN SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

The performance of a school is often linked to the principal's leadership role and there is a growing concern that most South African public schools are not functioning effectively. The observation is that principals hardly go to classrooms to check if teachers are attending their lessons Dongo (2016). This is a qualitative case study which explored teachers' perceptions on the role played by a principal's leadership regarding school improvement and academic performance. The study essentially interrogates the implications of principal's leadership role in school improvement and academic performance as perceived by teachers. This research is informed by School Management Theory of Leithwood, (2019). A sample of five participants was selected from a high school in Bloemfontein, in the Free State, in South Africa, using the purposeful sampling method. Data were collected through structured interviews with five experienced teachers. The data collected were analysed and grouped into themes, for further interpretation. The results showed that lack of school principals' leadership skills could lead to poor school academic performance as perceived by teachers. Teachers viewed the principals' leadership in schools as a significant variable that can strengthen and enhance school improvement and academic performance. The paper suggests that successful schools be led by a visible principal who communicates frequently about school pedagogical tasks. This study also serves as a guideline on principals' leadership and how effective school leadership serves as a platform that inculcates the virtues of good teacher and learner, for better school performance.

Keywords: Principal, leadership, perceptions, academic performance, school management, learners

1. INTRODUCTION

This study sought to explore the teachers' perceptions on the role played by their principal's leadership at a high school in South Africa. The study essentially interrogates the implications of principal's leadership role in school academic performance as perceived by teachers. It is the researchers' observation as Senior Education Specialists that most principals or school leaders are not effective in their leadership roles and their instructional leadership. However, there is a growing concern that most South African public schools are not functioning effectively, and an observation is that principals hardly go to classrooms to check if teachers are attending their lessons Dongo (2016). The performance of the school is often linked to principal's leadership role. This paper is guided by two research questions: 1: How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of principal's leadership role regarding school improvement and academic performance? 2:

How do teachers perceive the principal's instructional leadership role as improving school academic performance? The objective of this study is to establish the effectiveness of principal's leadership role regarding school improvement and academic performance as perceived by teachers.

1.1. The Statement of the Research Problem

There is increasing concern that few South African public schools are not operating successfully, and it has been noted that principals rarely visit classrooms to ensure that teachers are paying attention to their teachings, according to Dongo (2016). The performance of a school is often linked to the principal's leadership role. According to Chabalala and Naidoo (2021), there are concerns about both the effectiveness of principals' roles as instructional leaders and the quality of education provided by teachers. Teachers believe that a lack of support in classrooms by principals can lead to negative teacher perceptions about the principal's leadership, as well as other challenges in classrooms. It is not easy for teachers to work under these circumstances, despite the training that they received on how to work with learners.

1.2. The purpose of the study

The aim of this paper was to explore how a principal's leadership role is seen by teachers as it relates to improving academic performance in school.

1.3. The research objectives

The objective of this study was:

To observe how effective a principal's leadership role is in improving academic performance in a school as seen by teachers.

2. THE REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical framework

This research is informed by School Improvement Theory of Leithwood (2019). Leithwood, Harris and Hopkins, (2019) emphasize the links between leadership development and school results. This involves ensuring regular and timely attendance by learners and teachers, maintaining order and discipline in classrooms, and providing adequate resources to enable learning to take place.

2.2. Teachers' perceptions on effectiveness of principal's leadership role

According to Brown (2019) what affects school academic performance is that teachers do not get enough support from the principals. This can cause a downward spiral in teacher- commitment that can negatively affect their classroom management. Naidoo and Petersen (2015) asserted that the core business of schools are teaching and learning, and the core activity is the successful implementation of the curriculum.

Teachers believe that lack of support in classrooms from the principals can lead to negative teacher perceptions towards the principal's leadership role as well as more challenges in classrooms. It is not easy for teachers to work under such circumstances, despite the training that the teachers received regarding working with learners.

Good performance cannot be realized in educational institutions without appropriate leadership. This notion is also supported by the European Commission (2019) who argues that systems should provide opportunities for principal leaders to develop competences that support them in strategic thinking and planning. The concept of effective leadership is often associated with school effectiveness tradition. Central to the effective leadership in schools is the role of the principal. There is strong evidence suggesting that quality infrastructure facilitates better instructions, improves student's outcomes, and reduces dropout rates among other benefits. This is at variance with incessant demonstrations and complaints about alleged lack of resources and poor leadership within the schools.

Chalikias, Fotopoulos, Sidiropoulos, Kyriakopoulos, and Zakopoulos (2020) have elaborated on the role of the principal's leadership role in the improvement of school academic performance. Earlier, Taylor, Van der Berg and Mabogoane (2013) asserted that dysfunctional principal leadership in many schools may be an important reason for the low academic performance of South African students. Furthermore, the findings of this study could be applied to the management of education system in the Motheo District in Free State as principals play a critical role as change agents in creating positive working. The researchers selected a school that has been regarded as one of the performing schools in the Free State and a drop occurred in 2015. That school obtained a 54, 2%, as revealed by the Department of Basic Education South Africa.

(2016). The province regarded this school as underperforming. It was the researchers' assertion that a principal's leadership school improvement and academic performance plans in the Free State province were critical to an extent.

There appears to be a dearth in research on teachers' perceptions on the role played by principal's leadership and how best teachers can be supported to improve the school academic performance. Apparently, there is also a strong belief among educationists that principals can improve the teaching and learning environment by creating conditions conducive to improve curriculum management, Kiat, Tan, Heng & Lim-Ratnam (2017). Principals are responsible for creating positive school climates, motivating teachers, and learners, and effectively managing resources to enhance best instructional practices. Principals are faced with new demands, more complex decisions, and additional responsibilities than ever before. Their days are usually filled with diverse administrative and management functions such as procuring resources, managing learner discipline, resolving conflict with parents, and dealing with unexpected teacher and learner crises. Daries (2021) asserts that many school principals experience great difficulty in balancing their diverse administrative duties with their curriculum guidance. School principals in South African school setting are recognised as leaders and managers who have a great role to impact on the livelihood of their schools by setting the tone and ethos of teaching and learning activities. However, the nature of that work should reflect the school context and its needs at any one time.

The principal as the instructional leader is expected to set the instructional tone that must be followed by teachers and learners in pursuit of attainment of expected learner academic outcomes Mthiyane, Bhengu and Bayeni (2014). In setting such a tone, principals are expected to create effective communication channels with all stakeholders meant to confront matters of educator's performance in their teaching practice (Lefevre & Robinson 2015). Based on Leithwood's School Improvement theory, it can be argued that negative perceptions of teachers towards leadership will ultimately result in poor school performance. The researchers assert that effective leadership role yields positive outcomes in the followers Aydin, Sarier & Uysal (2013). In the next section, we discuss how principal's leadership role play a part in schools and in education.

Department of Education (2014) defines principal's leadership role as the central role to provide guidance and management to school. According to Mpungose and Ngwenya (2018) the functions and roles of the principal have been transformed to include those of both a leader and a manager. It is argued in this study that principals play important role as leader in schools Both definitions show that principal's role is of utmost importance in schools. We adopt the department of education definition for this study given the emphasis it places on guidance in schools, Sutton and Austin (2015) mission statement is that it wants to improve school performance. Effective principal's instructional leadership will play an important role in improving school academic performance.

DeMatthews (2014) defines instructional leadership as the principal's actions towards promotion of growth in teaching and learning. The school principals play a significant role in providing leadership in schools. Through instructional leadership, there is a clear setting of goals, managing curriculum, monitoring lesson plans, allocating resources, and evaluating of teachers regularly to promote student learning and growth. Contrastingly, it is common practice in township schools to see principals delegating instructional leadership roles to teachers while they focus on managerial tasks. This confirms the findings of Naidoo and Petersen (2015) that revealed that most of the principals view their work to be that of an organisation's manager. Principals are also involved in actual teaching and learning activities of the school to ensure quality teaching and learning. In the South African education context, the accountability of teaching and learning rests upon the principals' shoulders. Khumalo (2016) agrees that instructional leadership is the instrument for school improvement. If a school performs badly, the principal is the first to be evaluated, and harshly so. Looking at the definition of instructional leadership mentioned, one learns that the principal has a great influence on the teaching and learning process. Thus, teachers' working conditions including interactions with students and co-workers directly affects their productivity. School leaders should be accountable to improve their schools and to function as instructional leaders. However, Dongo (2016) revealed that there are some principals with a partial understanding of what instructional leadership entails.

Instructional leadership is a model of school leadership in which a principal works alongside teachers to provide support and guidance in establishing best practices in teaching, Brolund (2016). In the South African education context, the accountability of teaching and learning is on the principal's hands. When the school does not perform well, the principal must account. Available evidence suggests that South African educators spend far less time on actual teaching than the amount of time specified in policy. Hence principals must ensure that students are not deprived their right to education. Conversely, a key question for sustainable

principal's instructional leadership is when to make changes and what to give up making space for any new activity. Lastly, studies on instructional leadership (Lopez & Hossain 2021; Hallinger, Wang, Chen & Liare 2015; Mestry, Moonsammy-Koopasammy & Schmidt, 2013) seem to provide conflicting evidence regarding principal's understanding their key role in promoting curriculum delivery in their schools. Bush and Glover (2016) in their review of literature on school leadership in South Africa, opined that instructional leadership might be a proper route to follow for school improvement and academic performance. For Lopez & Hossain (2021) school principals should be present in person and virtually to address learners' and teachers' challenges creatively. Hence, the input of teachers in school improvement and in the effectiveness of principal's instructional leadership should not be ignored. Thus, this study sought to shed light on teachers' opinions regarding instructional leadership role of principal in enhancing learners' academic performance.

2.3. Research questions

This paper is guided by two research questions:

How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of principal's leadership role regarding school improvement and academic performance?

How do teachers perceive the principal's instructional leadership role as improving school academic performance?

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Paradigm

This study adopted the interpretive paradigm. The choice of this paradigm was largely influenced by the nature of the phenomenon to be studied and the assumptions that the researchers held about the issue under investigations. The interpretivist paradigm was chosen for this study because it recognizes the importance of social constructs, context, and time on human behaviour. The interpretivist paradigm afforded the researchers an opportunity to conduct the study in its environmental context and solicit the views, opinions, beliefs and perceptions of the teachers, learners and other members of the school management teams on the role that leadership plays in improving school academic performance. This paradigm also allowed the researcher to get to the subjective perceptions of the teachers on the role played by principal's leadership to improve the school performance, noting that the study itself does not seek to prove any theory or hypothesis.

3.2. Research Design and instruments

A qualitative research design was used in this study. The researchers felt the need to understand how teachers and principal embrace school academic situations. Aspers (2019) states that qualitative research is an iterative process in which improved understanding of the scientific community is achieved by making new significant distinctions resulting from getting closer to the phenomenon studied. The research was carried out through structured interviews by recording the information. Interviews were conducted with the teachers to assess their perceptions on role played by a principal's instructional leadership regarding school improvement and academic performance. Qualitative research design enables development of an understanding of the meaning that people ascribe to their experiences Austin and Sutton, (2015). Thus, to get multiple perspectives and an in depth understanding of the phenomenon under review, the researchers used the case study and structured interviews. The case study design assisted the researchers to understand better the social phenomenon of school principal leadership.

3.3. The Sample

Data for this study were collected from five experienced teachers from one school. This allowed the researchers to get in-depth information from these participants. These are individuals who the researchers end up interviewing. Moreover, a sample refers to units selected from a population. Kumar (2011) argues that it is not possible for a researcher to collect data from all cases in the population. A sample is selected and studied to understand the population from which the sample was drawn. Thus, there is a need to select a sample from the population. Only one high school was purposefully selected in the Motheo district in the Free State Province, South Africa. This sample was chosen because they are experienced in teaching and learning and in working under a principal. Thus, they were better placed to furnish the researcher with information on their perceptions on the role played by principal's leadership regarding school improvement and academic performance.

3.4. The Sampling Procedure

The researchers used a purposive sampling technique in selecting participants for this study. Purposive sampling method is based on the judgment of the researcher as to who will provide the best information to succeed for the objectives study indicated Etikan, Musa and Alkassim (2016). The researchers purposely selected five experienced teachers. For that reason, participants were able to give the information needed by the researchers in connection with the role played by principal's leadership regarding school improvement and academic performance. This was achieved by using several research instruments.

3.5. Data Collection Procedures

As part of the process of collection data, the researchers followed several steps to ensure that permission was granted; participants are invited and provide consent, and scheduling of face-to-face interviews. Finally, data were collected.

3.5.1 Scheduling of face-to-face interviews

The scheduling of face to face was done by the principal author. Five experienced teachers were interviewed. Appointments were set with each of the five respondents to conduct the face-to-face interviews at convenient times and venues. This was to ensure that each participant provided their own individual responses in their comfort and not influenced by others' perceptions in the process. The aim was to ensure that the data are credible, and conclusions drawn are more reflective of the overall views of educators that single most powerful educators in the group.

The studied school has weekly meetings where all experienced teachers attend. This was to ensure that the scheduling is seamless, and availability of all participants is secured as these meetings are already part of their weekly schedules. This went very well, and all participants were available on the scheduled dates. This entire process ensured that all data required for the study was collected effectively using the instruments as per the plan of this study. All completed interview schedules, focus discussion reports or recordings were retained by the researcher for data analysis. A conducive atmosphere was created by having an interviewee and interviewer in the interview room in a session.

3.6. Data Analysis Techniques

The research questions were answered through the collected data using the semi structured interviews with experienced teachers. The interviews involved dialogue with the researcher setting the agenda and asked questions and interviewee being cast in the role of respondent. The main researcher conducted all the interviews. The general aim in the interviews was for teachers to narrate their experiences with the principal's role in school improvement. Open ended questions were used to orient the participants. Data were thematically analysed in line with the research questions. The main researcher transcribed the interviews from her smartphone in the language used. The experienced teachers shared their views with the researcher on what they do in enhancing their perceptions and voiced their opinions on how the principal's leadership role affected the school academic performance as perceived by the teachers.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Research Questions Posed

As the reader shall recall, the study pursued two research questions:

Research question 1: How do teachers perceive the effectiveness of principals' leadership role regarding improvement of school academic performance?

The research questions were directed to the experienced teachers from one school. From the participants responses immersed the data yielded the following theme.

5. COMMUNICATION

The results of the study indicated that teachers play a supportive role by carrying out lawful instructions given by the principal. This is one of the important roles played by teachers in supporting the principals in their instructional leadership role for school improvement and academic performance. Thus, teachers perceive themselves as subject experts with a knowledge base in their subject area. The study also revealed that teachers implement what is required by the principals in supporting the principals to be effective leaders. Sharing important information was viewed to improve the school academic performance. Therefore, the traits a good teacher require that they generate deep understanding, critical thinking, and promote teamwork.

Despite teachers' involvement in supporting the principal's role, they did not view this as sufficient and as revealed by the interviews. It is evident from, Kiat, Tan, Heng & Lim-Ratnam (2017), reviewed that teachers support principals in improving the school academic performance.

Furthermore, the data collected also indicated that there is a need for teachers to play their role by working hand in hand with the principal to improve the school academic performance. In this case, teachers support the principal and positively make use of what they know about the principal's instructional leadership role in improving school academic performance by assisting where they can. The teachers carry out instructions issued by the principals and implement it. When principals share important information, this improved a school academic performance. Teachers also attain the set goals, assisting where they can avail themselves. Therefore, the findings herein revealed that teachers perceived principals' leadership role regarding improvement of school academic performance to be effective. This finding resonates with Mulyani, Meirawan, and Rahmadani, (2020) observation that the principal's leadership is a trigger of teaching performance in increasing school effectiveness.

Research question 2: How do teachers perceive the principal's instructional leadership role in improving school academic performance? From the participant's' responses emerged the following theme:

5.1 Principal's Instructional Leadership Role

The results of the study and the literature by Mthiyane, Bhengu and Bayeni (2014), The principal as the instructional leader is expected to set the instructional tone that must be followed by teachers and learners in pursuit of attainment of expected learner academic outcomes, indicated that principals are seen to be effective in their instructional leadership role as perceived by teachers. Findings point out that, dysfunctional principal's leadership in many schools may be an important reason for low academic performance as the principals are expected to have insight into their role as leaders, Hompashe (2018).

The principal plays a vital role in the school and needs the support from teachers. The chapter also found out that participants believed principal's instructional leadership gives teachers and learners a clear direction regarding academic improvement.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In summarizing teachers' perceptions on the role played by a principal's leadership regarding school improvement and academic performance in a high school in South Africa, the following conclusions were drawn:

The study concluded that the experienced teachers who participated in the study perceived themselves to be supportive by carrying out lawful instructions given by the principal. The researcher, therefore, conclude that as the paper explored the teachers' perceptions on the role played their principal's leadership at a high school in South Africa, the study essentially interrogated the implications of principal's leadership role in school academic performance as perceived by teachers. However, the results indicated that South African public schools are not functioning effectively, and an observation is that lack of school principal's leadership skills is a challenge identified that could lead to poor school academic performance as perceived by teachers. The researcher, therefore, concludes that the effectiveness of principal's leadership role addresses the various conditions regarding school improvement and academic performance. Secondly the paper strived to determine teachers' opinions on principal's instructional leadership role as improving school academic performance.

We suggest that schools must be led by visible principals who communicate frequently about school pedagogical tasks for success. Training sessions for principals on instructional leadership roles should be used in improving school academic performance.

6.1. RECOMMENDATIONS

Empirical findings indicate positive and negative experiences with regards to the principal's leadership role in school improvement and academic performance as perceived by teachers. The following recommendations are based on findings from the current study.

The study recommends that effective communication between the principals and the teachers in bringing school improvement and academic performance brought forth an area of interest in the light of effective principal's leadership role do teachers perceive the effectiveness of principals' leadership role, the responses of the experienced teachers evident that.

The researcher recommends that the role of principal's leadership should be strengthened while improving school academic performance. It will enlighten the department of Education that equip principals with skills and that will enable effective principal leadership role regarding improvement of school academic performance, this is evident by the responses from the SMT.

The researcher highly recommends that the principal as the instructional leader must set instructional tone by creating an effective communication channel. Once the leaders manage to strengthen their instructional leadership roles it can theoretically mediate the effectiveness of principal's instructional leadership and there will also be a quality of the relationship between teachers and the principals. Principals are second to teachers in their impact on school academic performance; some teachers do play their key role of carrying out instructions given by the principal in improving the school academic performance. Therefore, the paper recommends that developing a shared vision is one of the important roles played by principals in improving school academic performance. Teachers support the principal's instructional leadership in improving school academic performance. The study notes that dysfunctional principal's instructional leadership in many schools may be an important reason for low academic performance. Once principals fail to give teachers and learners clear direction, there will not be any achievement of school academic goals. The study recommends that training sessions for principals on instructional leadership roles will assist in improving school academic performance.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research was financially supported by ETDP.SETA 07/ETDPSETA/1/04/20.

<https://www.etdpseta.org.za/education>

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